

ENHANCING FIRE RESISTANCE OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES USING FUNCTIONALIZED AMMONIUM POLYPHOSPHATE NANOPARTICLES

Wenmu Yang¹, Jiawei Wang¹, Wenkai Chang¹, Mohammad S. Islam¹, Zhao Sha¹, Cheng Wang¹, Jin Zhang¹, Guan Heng Yeoh¹, Cyrille Boyer², Chun Hui Wang^{1*}

¹School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, University of New South Wales, Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia

²Cluster for Advanced Macromolecular Design, School of Chemical Engineering, High Street, UNSW Sydney, Australia

Email: chun.h.wang@unsw.edu.au, web page: <https://www.unsw.edu.au>

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ABSTRACT

Epoxy-based carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRPs) are widely used in aerospace, transportation, and construction due to their high strength-to-weight ratio. However, epoxy resins are flammable and can ignite and burn when exposed to fire, producing highly toxic smoke gases. The CFRPs' poor fire resistance is primarily due to the epoxy resin's inherent flammability. One common method to address this issue is to incorporate flame-retardant fillers into the matrix. However, existing flame-retardant particles typically range from tens to hundreds of microns, significantly decreasing the strength and fracture toughness of the composites.

To address this challenge, in this study, a novel strategy is proposed to functionalize ammonium polyphosphate (APP) with NH_3^+ groups from an amine-based hardener, yielding hardener-functionalized APP nanoparticles (HF-APP). These nanoparticles were further downsized from $14\mu\text{m}$ to $0.2\mu\text{m}$ by sonication and uniformly dispersed into the epoxy matrix of CFRPs. At a 30wt% loading, the modified composites exhibited a 50% reduction in peak heat release rate and an increase in the limiting oxygen index to 49. Additionally, substantial improvements were observed in flexural strength, short beam shear strength, and interlaminar fracture energy. Finite element analysis further revealed that HF-APP nanoparticles undergo filament-like separation at high stress levels, effectively mitigating interfacial stress concentration and preserving structural integrity. This multifunctional approach offers the significant potential for developing flame-retardant CFRPs capable of withstanding extreme environments while maintaining high mechanical and fracture properties, a feat previously unattainable with conventional methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxy resins and their composites are limited in their use in demanding fire protection environments due to the flammability of epoxy resins [1], their limiting oxygen index (LOI) is approximately 20%, rendering these materials extremely flammable even after the ignition source is removed [2]. This poses a serious threat to fire safety, especially in enclosed or high-risk environments such as rail tunnels and aircraft cabins. When exposed to fire, epoxy-based composites can undergo rapid thermal degradation, produce toxic smoke, and lose structural integrity, increasing the risk of structural failure, impeding evacuation and suppression measures. To mitigate these hazards, international flame-retardant standards have been established for materials used in railway vehicles and other public safety-critical areas, with emphasis on indicators such as ignition resistance, flame propagation, smoke release, and toxic gas emissions. However, meeting these standards while maintaining the high mechanical strength essential for structural performance remains a major engineering challenge.

To enhance the fire resistance of CFRPs, flame-retardant additives such as aluminium hydroxide, magnesium hydroxide, and APP are commonly incorporated into the matrix [3]. Organic additives,

including halogenated compounds and phosphorus-based molecules, are also widely used. While these approaches are effective in reducing flammability, high loadings (over 30wt%) are typically required hydroxide [4-6] which damage mechanical properties such as tensile and flexural strength. Moreover, the ununiform dispersion and weak interfacial bonding of large-sized additives (10 to 100 of microns) with the epoxy matrix can lead to stress concentrations and reduce fracture toughness [7]. Reactive strategies involving phosphorus, silicon, or halogen containing curing agents have been proposed to chemically integrate flame-retardant elements into the polymer network without significantly altering the resin's thermomechanical properties [6]. However, many of these approaches change the curing kinetics or final network structure of the epoxy, resulting in reduced stability or unpredictable performance.

In this study, we propose an innovative method to enhance the flame retardancy of epoxy and CFRP composites while maintaining or even improving their mechanical properties. APP particles were chemically functionalized via cationic ion exchange with NH_3^+ groups from an amine-based curing agent, yielding HF-APP particles [8]. This functionalization enabled the particles to participate in the curing reaction with epoxy, improving compatibility and interfacial adhesion with the epoxy matrix. The particles were further downsized via probe ultrasonication and filtration, resulting in submicron nanoparticles denoted as SHF-APP with improved dispersibility. Composites fabricated using these modified particles exhibited significantly enhanced flame-retardant performance, including a 50% reduction in peak heat release rate and a LOI value up to 49, while maintaining over 90% of the tensile strength of neat epoxy at 20wt% HF-APP loading. Mechanical tests further demonstrated improved flexural strength, short beam shear strength, and interlaminar fracture energy. Finite element analysis revealed that HF-APP particles can deform or split under stress, reducing their stress concentration effects and minimizing mechanical compromise. These results highlight the dual functionality of HF-APP in simultaneously curing and reinforcing the epoxy matrix, offering a potential solution for high-performance, fire-safe CFRP structures in transportation and construction industries.

2 GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS

2.1 Material and methods

The materials used in this study include bisphenol A-type epoxy resin (DGEBA), APP, and an amine-based hardener. APP was surface functionalized via mixing with the curing agent, enhancing its compatibility with the epoxy matrix. The functionalized APP was further downsized to nanoparticles and then incorporated into the epoxy resin at various loadings (10–30wt%) to prepare the modified systems. CFRP laminates were further fabricated using a hand lay-up process followed by vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM). The flame-retardant performance of the composites was characterized by LOI, UL-94 vertical burning tests, and cone calorimetry, while mechanical properties were evaluated through tensile, flexural, and interlaminar shear strength tests. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was employed to analyze the morphology and dispersion of the modified particles within the matrix.

2.2 Results and discussion

2.2.1 Flame retardant tests results

The flame-retardant performance of epoxy matrix was significantly enhanced by incorporating HF-APP. In cone calorimetry, neat epoxy exhibited a peak heat release rate (PHRR) of 1841 kW/m² and a total heat release (THR) of 62.4 MJ/m². With 30wt% HF-APP, the PHRR drastically dropped to 37 kW/m², and the composite self-extinguished during testing, with THR approaching zero. In contrast, unmodified APP only reduced the PHRR to 856 kW/m² at the same loading. The total smoke release (TSR) was also significantly reduced by HF-APP, achieving a 95% decrease at 30wt% loading, compared to a 50% reduction by APP. The LOI increased from 20 (neat epoxy) to 44 for HF-APP/epoxy composites at 30wt%, highlighting their resistance to ignition.

For CFRP systems, the PHRR was reduced from 408 kW/m² (unmodified epoxy matrix) to 103 kW/m² with 30wt% HF-APP. LOI values rose from 36 to 49. Notably, only 10wt% HF-APP was sufficient to achieve the highest V-0 rating in UL-94 vertical burning tests, whereas 30wt% APP or 20wt% SHF-APP was required for the same level. The flame-retardant performance of SHF-APP composites was found to be intermediate between that of APP and HF-APP. While the further reduction in particle size led to a slight increase in PHRR, it also resulted in a decrease in THR, indicating a balance effect in performance matrix. Overall, SHF-APP exhibited flame-retardant behavior comparable to HF-APP, suggesting that the nanoscale particle size maintains thermal protection while offering potential advantages in mechanical reinforcement. These results highlight SHF-APP as an effective alternative that balances flame retardancy with enhanced structural performance.

Fig. 1 LOI values of CFRPs with different weight loadings of APP, HF-APP, and SHF-APP in the epoxy matrix.

Fig. 2 Char residues: neat epoxy (a), 20 wt% APP/epoxy (b), 20 wt% HF-APP/epoxy (c) and weight percentage of residues (d) from cone calorimeter tests.

2.2.2 Mechanical tests results

The mechanical performance of CFRPs incorporating APP, HF-APP, and SHF-APP were systematically evaluated through tensile, short beam shear, and interlaminar fracture tests. The short beam shear strength was largely preserved even at high additive concentrations. Both APP and HF-APP modified composites maintained over 90% of the strength of the unmodified laminate at 30wt%. Notably, SHF-APP led to a 30% increase in short beam shear strength, attributed to more uniform matrix distribution, reduced interlaminar cracking, and improved fibre alignment. Interlaminar fracture energy (G_{IC}) was also investigated, showing that while APP and HF-APP caused moderate reductions at higher loadings, SHF-APP at 30wt% retained nearly the full fracture toughness of the baseline CFRP. These results indicate that HF-APP improves strength retention in epoxy matrices, and SHF-APP enhances interlaminar properties in CFRPs, offering a potential method to flame-retardant composites with minimal reduction in mechanical performance.

Fig. 3 Strengths of CFRPs with different weight loadings of APP, HF-APP, and SHF-APP particles: tensile strength (a) and flexural strength (b).

Fig. 4 Short beam shear strength (a) of CFRP with different weight concentrations of APP, HF-APP, and SHF-APP. Microscopic optical images of samples' cross sections of CFRP (b) and CFRP with 30wt% APP (c), HF-APP (d), and SHF-APP (d) after short beam shear test.

2.2.3 Comparison of the key results

A comparative analysis of mechanical strength retention and flame-retardant performance was conducted for epoxy matrix and CFRP systems incorporating unmodified APP, HF-APP, and SHF-APP, alongside other modification strategies such as ATNi [9], and DDM [10] functionalized APP. In the epoxy matrix system, tensile tests revealed that at 10wt% loading, HF-APP achieved the highest retention of mechanical strength, closely matching the performance of APP@ATNi, while also delivering the most obvious reduction in PHRR. HF-APP exhibited comparable enhancements in LOI, char residue, and total heat release (THR), demonstrating its balanced improvement in both structural and flame-retardant properties.

Fig. 5 Comparisons of the unmodified APP and HF-APP with APP@ ATNi and APP@DDM at 10wt% loading.

In contrast, SHF-APP demonstrated the best mechanical advantages. Specifically, the short beam shear strength and interlaminar fracture toughness were significantly improved by SHF-APP compared to both APP and HF-APP, while maintaining flame-retardant effectiveness equivalent to HF-APP. Furthermore, the cumulative percentage changes across seven key performance indicators highlighted SHF-APP as the most balanced and effective additive for CFRP applications. These results suggest that while HF-APP is optimal for preserving tensile performance in epoxy matrices, SHF-APP particles are more suitable for CFRP composites where interlaminar properties and fire safety must be simultaneously optimized.

Fig. 6 Comparison of the mechanical and fire-retardant performance indicators of the four types of CFRPs.

3 CONCLUSION

In this study, a novel strategy was developed to enhance the flame-retardant performance and retain the mechanical integrity of epoxy resins and their CFRPs through the functionalization of APP using an amine-based curing agent. In the epoxy system, the resulting HF-APP exhibited strong interfacial compatibility with the matrix and a filamentous morphology that effectively mitigated stress concentrations. At 20wt% loading, HF-APP reduced the peak heat release rate and total heat release by 87% and 83%, respectively, while maintaining 92% of the tensile strength of the neat epoxy. By reducing the average particle size of HF-APP from 14 μm to 0.12 μm via probe ultrasonication, SHF-APP particles were obtained. These particles preserved the flame-retardant performance of HF-APP while further improving short beam shear strength and interlaminar fracture toughness due to enhanced matrix uniformity and fibre alignment. These improvements were attributed to improved dispersion, stress transfer, and the formation of dense char layers during combustion. The modified system met the highest fire safety classification (HL3) under EN 45545-2:2013, demonstrating its suitability for railway applications. The findings of this study provide new insights into the structure–property relationships of flame-retardant fillers in polymer composites, offering potential methods for developing multifunctional CFRPs that meet both fire safety standards and mechanical performance requirements for applications in transportation, infrastructure, and high-performance engineering.

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